

A Note on Neutrosophic Submodule of an R -module M

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Abstract

The paper focuses on the applications of neutrosophic set theory in the domain of classical algebraic structures, especially R -module. This study discusses some algebraic operations of neutrosophic sets of an R -module M , induced by the operations in M and demonstrates certain properties of the neutrosophic submodules of an R -module. The ideas of R module's non-empty arbitrary family of neutrosophic submodules are characterized, and related outcomes are proved. The last section of this paper also derives a necessary and sufficient condition for a neutrosophic set of an R -module M .

Keywords: R -module, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Submodule, Support, Neutrosophic Point

1 Introduction

Traditionally the set theory deals with sets of objects, their features and framework models of axioms. Practical problems in research, science and economics cannot be solved in the current environment due to the inadequacy of the ideas of parameterisation techniques. In 1965, Lotfi Aliaskar Zadeh [1] published a paper describing the concept of imprecise boundaries of sets which led to the emergence of fuzzy set theory. After the implementation of fuzzy sets by Zadeh, this basic notion has been generalized in several ways. In 1986 Atanassov [2] put forward intuitionistic fuzzy set theory as a stereotype illustration of a set in which each component is concomitant with membership and non-membership grades. In 1995, the University of New Mexico's scientist and mathematics professor Florentin Smarandache [3] inspired by sport matches (winning / defeating / tie scores), votes (pro / counter / null or black votes), decision making (accept / reject / pending) and control theory (yes / no / not relevant) coined a new idea and a branch of philosophy called neutrosophy. Neutrosophy means understanding neutral concepts and extending of tri-valued logic by non-standard analysis [4, 5].

The main objective of the neutrosophic set is to narrow the gap between the vague, ambiguous and imprecise real-world situations. Neutrosophic set theory gives a thorough scientific and mathematical model knowledge in which speculative and uncertain hypothetical phenomena can be managed by hierarchal membership of the components " truth / indeterminacy / falsehood " [4, 6]. Among the different branches of applied and pure mathematics, abstract algebra was one of the first few areas where research was conducted using the concept of neutrosophic set. Some authors have studied the algebraic structure associated in pure mathematics with uncertainty. In 1971, Azriel Rosenfeld [7] presented a seminal paper on fuzzy subgroup and W.J. Liu [8] developed the idea of fuzzy normal subgroup and fuzzy subring. It was a significant milestone in the area of mathematics research and fuzzy algebra. Mordeson's and Malik's book [9] gives an account of all these concepts upto 1998. Negoita and Ralescu [10] launched the notion of a fuzzy module. Then fuzzy module was further developed by Mashinchi & Zahedi [11]. The idea of a direct sum of fuzzy modules was investigated by P. Isaac [12]. In 2011 P. Isaac, P.P.John [13] studied about the algebraic nature of intuitionistic fuzzy submodule of a classical module.

The consolidation of the neutrosophic set hypothesis with algebraic structures is a growing trend in mathematical research. One of the key developments in the neutrosophic set theory is the hybridization of the neutrosophic set with various potential algebraic structures such as bipolar set, soft set and hesitant fuzzy set [14–16]. W. B. Vasantha Kandasamy and Florentin Smarandache [17] initially presented basic neutrosophic algebraic structures and their application. Vidan Cetkin [18, 19] consolidated the neutrosophic set theory and algebraic

structures, creating neutrosophic subgroups and neutrosophic submodules. The basic features of single valued neutrosophic submodules of an R -module (classical module) are studied by Cetkin and Olgun N [19, 20]. Neutrosophic algebraic structures have higher expressive power than classical crisp set-based structures. This paper explains certain elementary properties of neutrosophic set of an R -module M and characteristics of neutrosophic submodule of an R -module M .

Neutrosophic set generalizes a classical set, fuzzy set, interval-valued fuzzy set and intuitionistic fuzzy set that can be used to make a mathematical model for the real problems of science and engineering. The remaining of the paper is structured as follows. The section 2 briefs about neutrosophic set operations and neutrosophic sub-modules of an R -module M . Section 3 provides some elementary properties of neutrosophic set of an R -module M and related results. The findings and description of the related work are also briefed in section 4. Finally section 5 presents a valid summary and future work of the proposed study.

2 Preliminaries

This section presents some of the preliminary definitions and results which are basic for a better and clear cognizance of next chapters.

Definition 2.1. [21] Let R be a commutative ring with unity. A module M over R is an abelian group with a law of composition written '+' and a scalar multiplication $R \times M \rightarrow M$, written $(r, x) \rightsquigarrow rx$, that satisfy these axioms

1. $1x = x$
2. $(rs)x = r(sx)$
3. $(r + s)x = rx + sx$
4. $r(x + y) = rx + ry \quad \forall r, s \in R$ and $x, y \in M$.

Definition 2.2. [21] A submodule N of an R -module M is a nonempty subset that is closed under addition and scalar multiplication, i.e., $x_1 + x_2 \in N$, $rx \in N \quad \forall r \in R, x_1, x_2, x \in N$.

Definition 2.3. [22] Let A and B be submodules of an R -module M . The sum of A and B , denoted as a set $A + B = \{x + y : x \in A, y \in B\}$ which is also a submodule and smallest submodule which contains both A and B .

Theorem 2.1. [22] The intersection of any non empty collection of submodules of an R -module is a submodule.

Definition 2.4. [4] A neutrosophic set P of the universal set X is defined as $P = \{(x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x)) : x \in X\}$ where $t_P, i_P, f_P : X \rightarrow (-0, 1^+)$. The three components t_P, i_P and f_P represent membership value (Percentage of truth), indeterminacy (Percentage of indeterminacy) and non membership value (Percentage of falsity) respectively. These components are functions of non standard unit interval $(-0, 1^+)$.

Remark 2.1. [23,24] "If $t_P, i_P, f_P : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, then P is known as Single Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS).

Remark 2.2. This paper considers only SVNS. For simplicity SVNS will be called neutrosophic set.

Remark 2.3. U^X denotes the set of all neutrosophic subsets of X or neutrosophic power set of X .

Definition 2.5. [4,25] Let P and Q be two neutrosophic sets of X . Then P is contained in Q , denoted as $P \subseteq Q$ if and only if $P(x) \leq Q(x) \quad \forall x \in X$, this means that $t_P(x) \leq t_Q(x)$, $i_P(x) \leq i_Q(x)$, $f_P(x) \geq f_Q(x)$, $\forall x \in X$

Definition 2.6. [4,26] The complement of a neutrosophic set $P = \{x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x) : x \in X\}$ of X is denoted and defined as $P^c = \{x, f_P(x), 1 - i_P(x), t_P(x) : x \in X\}$.

Definition 2.7. [4,27] Let $P, Q \in U^X \quad \forall x \in X$. Then

1. The union C of P and Q is denoted by $C = P \cup Q$ and defined as $C(x) = P(x) \vee Q(x)$ where $C(x) = \{x, t_C(x), i_C(x), f_C(x) : x \in X\}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} t_C(x) &= t_P(x) \vee t_Q(x) \\ i_C(x) &= i_P(x) \vee i_Q(x) \\ f_C(x) &= f_P(x) \wedge f_Q(x) \end{aligned}$$

2. The intersection C of P and Q is denoted by $C = P \cap Q$ and is defined as $C(x) = P(x) \wedge Q(x)$ where $C(x) = \{x, t_C(x), i_C(x), f_C(x) : x \in X\}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} t_C(x) &= t_P(x) \wedge t_Q(x) \\ i_C(x) &= i_P(x) \wedge i_Q(x) \\ f_C(x) &= f_P(x) \vee f_Q(x) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.8. [28] Let P and Q be neutrosophic sets of an R -Module M . Then their sum $P + Q$ is a neutrosophic set of M , defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} P + Q(x) &= \{x, t_{P+Q}(x), i_{P+Q}(x), f_{P+Q}(x) : x \in M\} \text{ where} \\ t_{P+Q}(x) &= \vee \{t_P(y) \wedge t_Q(z) | x = y + z, y, z \in M\} \\ i_{P+Q}(x) &= \vee \{i_P(y) \wedge i_Q(z) | x = y + z, y, z \in M\} \\ f_{P+Q}(x) &= \wedge \{f_P(y) \vee f_Q(z) | x = y + z, y, z \in M\}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.9. [19] Let P be a neutrosophic set of an R -module M and $r \in R$. Define neutrosophic set $rP = \{x, t_{rP}(x), i_{rP}(x), f_{rP}(x) : x \in M\}$ of M as follows

$$\begin{aligned} t_{rP}(x) &= \begin{cases} \vee \{t_P(y)\} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}; \quad i_{rP}(x) = \\ & \begin{cases} \vee \{i_P(y)\} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad f_{rP}(x) = \begin{cases} \wedge \{f_P(y)\} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

3 Neutrosophic Set of an R -module M

In this section a few algebraic properties of neutrosophic submodules of an R -module M are demonstrated and evaluated using three different membership grade values of neutrosophic submodules.

Definition 3.1. [19] Let M be an R module. Let $P \in U^M$ where U^M denotes the neutrosophic power set of R -module M . Then a neutrosophic subset $P = \{x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x) : x \in M\}$ in M is called neutrosophic submodule of M if it satisfies the following;

1. $t_P(0) = 1, i_P(0) = 1, f_P(0) = 0$
2. $t_P(x + y) \geq t_P(x) \wedge t_P(y)$
 $i_P(x + y) \geq i_P(x) \wedge i_P(y)$
 $f_P(x + y) \leq f_P(x) \vee f_P(y), \forall x, y \in M$
3. $t_P(rx) \geq t_P(x), i_P(rx) \geq i_P(x), f_P(rx) \leq f_P(x), \forall x \in M, \forall r \in R$.

Remark 3.1. The set of all neutrosophic submodules of R -module M represented by $U(M)$.

Example 3.1. [19] Consider the classical ring $R = \mathbb{Z}_4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Since each ring is a module on itself, take $R = \mathbb{Z}_4$ as a classical module. Define the single valued neutrosophic set P as follows $P = \{(0, \langle 1, 1, 0 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.6 \rangle), (2, \langle 0.8, 0.1, 0.4 \rangle), (3, \langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.6 \rangle)\}$. Then the neutrosophic set P is a neutrosophic submodule of M .

Definition 3.2. [19] Let M be an R module. Let $P \in U^M$ where U^M denotes the neutrosophic power set of R -module M . Then a neutrosophic subset $P = \{x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x) : x \in M\}$ in M is called neutrosophic submodule of M if it satisfies the following;

1. $t_P(0) = 1, i_P(0) = 1, f_P(0) = 0$
2. $t_P(x + y) \geq t_P(x) \wedge t_P(y)$
 $i_P(x + y) \geq i_P(x) \wedge i_P(y)$
 $f_P(x + y) \leq f_P(x) \vee f_P(y), \forall x, y \in M$
3. $t_P(rx) \geq t_P(x), i_P(rx) \geq i_P(x), f_P(rx) \leq f_P(x), \forall x \in M, \forall r \in R$.

Remark 3.2. The set of all neutrosophic submodules of R -module M represented by $U(M)$.

Theorem 3.1. [19] Let P be a neutrosophic set of M . Then $P \in U(M)$ if and only if the following properties are satisfied $\forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R$

- i) $t_P(0) = 1, i_P(0) = 1, f_P(0) = 0$
- ii) $t_P(rx + sy) \geq t_P(x) \wedge t_P(y); i_P(rx + sy) \geq i_P(x) \wedge i_P(y);$
 $f_P(rx + sy) \leq f_P(x) \vee f_P(y)$.

Definition 3.3. For any neutrosophic subset $P = \{(x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x)) : x \in X\}$ of X , the support P^* of the neutrosophic set P can be defined as

$$P^* = \{x \in X, t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1\}.$$

Proposition 3.1. Let $P, Q \in U^X$. If $P \subseteq Q$, then $P^* \subseteq Q^*$.

Proof. Given that $P \subseteq Q$, then $t_P(x) \leq t_Q(x) : i_P(x) \leq i_Q(x) : f_P(x) \geq f_Q(x) \forall x \in X$. Consider $x \in P^*$, then, $t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1$. So it can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} t_Q(x) &\geq t_P(x) > 0 \\ i_Q(x) &\geq i_P(x) > 0 \\ f_Q(x) &\leq f_P(x) < 1 \end{aligned}$$

So that $x \in Q^*$, $\therefore P^* \subseteq Q^*$. Hence proved. □

Proposition 3.2. Let $P = \{x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x); x \in M\}$ be a neutrosophic set of M , then $t_{rP}(rx) \geq t_P(x), i_{rP}(rx) \geq i_P(x)$ and $f_{rP}(rx) \leq f_P(x)$.

Proof. Consider

$$t_{rP}(rx) = \vee\{t_P(y) : y \in M, rx = ry\} \geq t_P(x), \forall x \in M$$

Similarly $i_{rP}(rx) \geq i_P(x)$. Also

$$f_{rP}(rx) = \wedge\{f_P(y) : y \in M, rx = ry\} \leq f_P(x), \forall x \in M$$

Hence the proof. □

Proposition 3.3. If $P, Q \in U^M$, then $\forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R$

1. $t_{(rP+sQ)}(rx + sy) \geq t_P(x) \wedge t_Q(y)$
2. $i_{(rP+sQ)}(rx + sy) \geq i_P(x) \wedge i_Q(y)$
3. $f_{(rP+sQ)}(rx + sy) \leq f_P(x) \wedge f_Q(y)$

Proof. 1. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} t_{(rP+sQ)}(rx + sy) &= \bigvee\{t_{rP}(\vartheta_1) \wedge t_{sQ}(\vartheta_2) : \vartheta_1, \vartheta_2 \in M, \vartheta_1 + \vartheta_2 = rx + sy\} \\ &\geq t_{rP}(rx) \wedge t_{sQ}(sy) \\ &\geq t_P(x) \wedge t_Q(y) \forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R. \end{aligned}$$

2. Same as above.

3. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} f_{(rP+sQ)}(rx + sy) &= \bigwedge\{f_{rP}(\vartheta_1) \vee f_{sQ}(\vartheta_2) : \vartheta_1, \vartheta_2 \in M, \vartheta_1 + \vartheta_2 = rx + sy\} \\ &\leq f_{rP}(rx) \vee f_{sQ}(sy) \\ &\leq f_P(x) \vee f_Q(y) \forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the proof. □

Definition 3.4. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be an arbitrary non empty family of U^M where $P_i = \{x, t_{P_i}(x), i_{P_i}(x), f_{P_i}(x) : x \in M\}$ for each $i \in J$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in J} P_i &= \{x, t_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x), i_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x), f_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) : x \in M\} \text{ where} \\ t_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \vee\{\bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x\} \forall x \in M \\ i_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \vee\{\bigwedge_{i \in J} i_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x\} \forall x \in M \\ f_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \wedge\{\bigvee_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x\} \forall x \in M \end{aligned}$$

in $\sum_{i \in J} x_i$, at most finitely x_i 's are not equal to zero.

Proposition 3.4. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be an arbitrary non empty family of U^M , then $r(\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i) = \bigcup_{i \in J} (rP_i)$ for $r \in R$.

Proof. Consider $r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i = \{x, t_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x), i_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x), f_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x) : x \in M, r \in R\}$
 Now

$$\begin{aligned} t_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \begin{cases} \bigvee \{t_{\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(y) & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \bigvee \{ \bigvee_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(y) \} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \bigvee_{i \in J} t_{rP_i}(x) \\ &= t_{\bigcup_{i \in J} rP_i}(x) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly $i_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x) = i_{\bigcup_{i \in J} rP_i}(x)$
 Now

$$\begin{aligned} f_{r \bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \begin{cases} \bigwedge \{f_{\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i}(y) \} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \bigwedge \{ \bigwedge_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(y) \} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \bigwedge_{i \in J} f_{rP_i}(x) \\ &= f_{\bigcup_{i \in J} rP_i}(x) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $r(\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i) = \bigcup_{i \in J}(rP_i)$ for $r \in R$. □

Definition 3.5. For any $x \in X$, the neutrosophic point $\hat{N}_{\{x\}}$ is defined as $\hat{N}_{\{x\}}(s) = \{s, t_{\hat{N}_{\{x\}}}(s), i_{\hat{N}_{\{x\}}}(s), f_{\hat{N}_{\{x\}}}(s) : s \in X\}$ where

$$\hat{N}_{\{x\}}(s) = \begin{cases} (1, 1, 0) & x = s \\ (0, 0, 1) & x \neq s \end{cases}$$

Remark 3.3. Let X be a non empty set. The neutrosophic point $\hat{N}_{\{0\}}$ in X is $\hat{N}_{\{0\}}(x) = \{x, t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), i_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) : x \in X\}$ where

$$\hat{N}_{\{0\}}(x) = \begin{cases} (1, 1, 0) & x = 0 \\ (0, 0, 1) & x \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

Proposition 3.5. Let $\hat{N}_{\{0\}}$ be the neutrosophic point in X . Then $r\hat{N}_{\{0\}} = \hat{N}_{\{0\}} \forall r \in R$.

Proof. Consider $r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}(x) = \{x, t_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), i_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), f_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) : x \in M\}$, where $\forall r \in R$ and

$$\begin{aligned} t_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) &= \bigvee \{t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(y) : y \in M, x = ry\} \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & x = 0 \\ 0 & x \neq 0 \end{cases} \\ &= t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \forall x \in M \end{aligned}$$

Similarly it can prove that, $i_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) = i_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x)$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{r\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) &= \bigwedge \{f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(y) : y \in M, x = ry\} \\ &= \begin{cases} 0 & x = 0 \\ 1 & x \neq 0 \end{cases} \\ &= f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \forall x \in M \end{aligned}$$

Hence for any $r \in R$, $r\hat{N}_{\{0\}} = \hat{N}_{\{0\}}$. □

Theorem 3.2. Let $P \in U^X$. $P = \hat{N}_{\{0\}}$ if and only if $P^* = \{0\}$.

Proof. If $P = \hat{N}_{\{0\}}$, then $P^* = (x \in X, t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1) = \{0\}$.
 Conversely, if $P^* = \{0\} \Rightarrow t_P(0) > 0, i_P(0) > 0, f_P(x) < 1$ and $t_P(x) = 0, i_P(x) = 0$ and $f_P(x) = 1 \forall x \neq 0$. Therefore

$$P(x) = \begin{cases} (1, 1, 0) & x = 0 \\ (0, 0, 1) & x \neq 0 \end{cases} = \hat{N}_{\{0\}}$$

Hence the proof. □

Definition 3.6. For any neutrosophic subset $P = \{(x, t_P(x), i_P(x), f_P(x)) : x \in X\}$ of X , the support P^* of the neutrosophic set P can be defined as

$$P^* = \{x \in X, t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1\}.$$

Proposition 3.6. Let $P, Q \in U^X$. If $P \subseteq Q$, then $P^* \subseteq Q^*$.

Proof. Given that $P \subseteq Q$, then $t_P(x) \leq t_Q(x) : i_P(x) \leq i_Q(x) : f_P(x) \geq f_Q(x) \forall x \in X$. Consider $x \in P^*$, then $t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1$. So it can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} t_Q(x) &\geq t_P(x) > 0 \\ i_Q(x) &\geq i_P(x) > 0 \\ f_Q(x) &\leq f_P(x) < 1 \end{aligned}$$

So that $x \in Q^*$, $\therefore P^* \subseteq Q^*$. Hence the proof. □

Definition 3.7. Let $P \in U^X$. If for all $\beta \in [0, 1]$, the β -level sets of P , can be denoted and defined as $P_\beta = \{x \in X : t_P(x) \geq \beta, i_P(x) \geq \beta, f_P(x) \leq \beta\}$ and the strict β level sets of P can be denoted and defined as $P_\beta^* = \{x \in X : t_P(x) > \beta, i_P(x) > \beta, f_P(x) < \beta\}$.

Proposition 3.7. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be an arbitrary non empty family of U^X . Then for any $\beta \in [0, 1]$, then

1. $\bigcap_{i \in J} (P_i)_\beta = (\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i)_\beta$
2. $\bigcup_{i \in J} (P_i)_\beta \subseteq (\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i)_\beta$

Proof. 1. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} x \in \bigcap_{i \in J} (P_i)_\beta &\Leftrightarrow x \in (P_i)_\beta \forall i \in J \\ &\Leftrightarrow t_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, i_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, f_{P_i}(x) \leq \beta \forall i \in J \\ &\Leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, \bigwedge_{i \in J} i_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, \bigvee_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(x) \leq \beta \\ &\Leftrightarrow t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \geq \beta, i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \geq \beta, f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \leq \beta \\ &\Leftrightarrow x \in (\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i)_\beta \end{aligned}$$

2. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} x \in \bigcup_{i \in J} (P_i)_\beta &\Rightarrow x \in (P_j)_\beta \text{ for some } j \in J \\ &\Rightarrow t_{P_j}(x) \geq \beta, i_{P_j}(x) \geq \beta, f_{P_j}(x) \leq \beta \\ &\Rightarrow \bigvee_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, \bigvee_{i \in J} i_{P_i}(x) \geq \beta, \bigwedge_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(x) \leq \beta \\ &\Rightarrow x \in (\bigcup_{i \in J} P_i)_\beta \end{aligned}$$

Hence the proof. □

4 Neutrosophic Submodule of an R -module M

This section explains the characteristics of neutrosophic submodules of an R -module and some associated results and theorems.

Theorem 4.1. Let $P \in U(M)$. Then P^* is a submodule of M .

Proof. Given $P \in U(M)$ and $P^* = \{x \in M, t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1\}$. Let $x, \theta \in P^*$. Then
 $t_P(x) > 0, i_P(x) > 0, f_P(x) < 1$
 $t_P(\theta) > 0, i_P(\theta) > 0, f_P(\theta) < 1$

To prove that $rx + s\theta \in P^*$ where $r, s \in R$.

i.e. to prove that $t_P(rx + s\theta) > 0, i_P(rx + s\theta) > 0$, and $f_P(rx + s\theta) < 1$.

Now

$$\begin{aligned} t_P(rx + s\theta) &\geq t_P(rx) \wedge t_P(s\theta) \\ &\geq t_P(x) \wedge t_P(\theta) > 0. \end{aligned}$$

The remaining two inequalities can be proved in the same way.

Hence P^* is a submodule of M . □

Theorem 4.2. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be an arbitrary non empty family of $U(M)$, then $\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i \in U(M)$.

Proof. Consider $\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i = \{x, t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x), i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x), f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) : x \in M\}$ and $t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(0) = \bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(0) = 1$; $i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(0) = \bigwedge_{i \in J} i_{P_i}(0) = 1$; $f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(0) = \bigvee_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(0) = 0$ Now, $\forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(rx + sy) &= \bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(rx + sy) \\ &\geq \bigwedge_{i \in J} (t_{P_i}(x) \wedge t_{P_i}(y)) \\ &= [\bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(x)] \wedge [\bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(y)] \\ &= t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \wedge t_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(y) \end{aligned}$$

in the same way it can derive

$$\begin{aligned} i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(rx + sy) &\geq i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \wedge i_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(y) \\ f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(rx + sy) &\leq f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(x) \vee f_{\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i}(y) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\bigcap_{i \in J} P_i \in U(M)$ □

Remark 4.1. If $P, Q \in U(M)$, then $P \cap Q \in U(M)$.

Definition 4.1. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be an arbitrary non empty family of U^M where $P_i = \{x, t_{P_i}(x), i_{P_i}(x), f_{P_i}(x) : x \in M\}$ for each $i \in J$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in J} P_i &= \{x, t_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x), i_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x), f_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) : x \in M\} \text{ where} \\ t_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \bigvee \{ \bigwedge_{i \in J} t_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x \} \forall x \in M \\ i_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \bigvee \{ \bigwedge_{i \in J} i_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x \} \forall x \in M \\ f_{\sum_{i \in J} P_i}(x) &= \bigwedge \{ \bigvee_{i \in J} f_{P_i}(x_i) : x_i \in M, \sum_{i \in J} x_i = x \} \forall x \in M \end{aligned}$$

in $\sum_{i \in J} x_i$, at most finitely x_i 's are not equal to zero.

Theorem 4.3. If $P, Q \in U(M)$, then $P + Q \in U(M)$.

Proof. It is enough to prove that $P + Q$ satisfies the following conditions $\forall x, y \in M, r, s \in R$

1. $t_{P+Q}(0) = 1, i_{P+Q}(0) = 1, f_{P+Q}(0) = 0$
2. $t_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \geq t_{P+Q}(x) \wedge t_{P+Q}(y), i_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \geq i_{P+Q}(x) \wedge i_{P+Q}(y),$
 $f_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \leq f_{P+Q}(x) \vee f_{P+Q}(y)$

Since $P, Q \in U(M)$, from the definition 2.8, condition 1 is obvious.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{P+Q}(x) \wedge t_{P+Q}(y) &= \bigvee \{t_P(x_1) \wedge t_Q(x_2) : x = x_1 + x_2\} \wedge \\
 &\quad \bigvee \{t_P(y_1) \wedge t_Q(y_2) : y = y_1 + y_2\} \\
 &\leq \bigvee \{t_P(rx_1) \wedge t_Q(rx_2) : rx = rx_1 + rx_2\} \wedge \\
 &\quad \bigvee \{t_P(sy_1) \wedge t_Q(sy_2) : sy = sy_1 + sy_2\} \\
 &= \bigvee \{[t_P(rx_1) \wedge t_P(sy_1)] \wedge [t_Q(rx_2) \wedge t_Q(sy_2)] \\
 &\quad : rx = rx_1 + rx_2, sy = sy_1 + sy_2\} \\
 &\leq \bigvee \{t_P(rx_1 + sy_1) \wedge t_Q(rx_2 + sy_2) \\
 &\quad : rx + sy = rx_1 + sy_1 + rx_2 + sy_2\} \\
 &= t_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \text{ where } rx + sy = r(x_1 + x_2) + s(y_1 + y_2) \\
 &\quad \forall x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in M
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $i_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \geq i_{P+Q}(x) \wedge i_{P+Q}(y)$; $f_{P+Q}(rx + sy) \leq f_{P+Q}(x) \vee f_{P+Q}(y)$
 $\therefore P + Q \in U(M)$. □

Corollary 4.3.1. Let $P_i, i \in J$ be a family of neutrosophic submodules of an R -module M . Then $\sum_{i \in J} P_i \in U(M)$.

Corollary 4.3.2. Let $P, Q \in U(M)$, then

1. $(P + Q)^* = P^* + Q^*$
2. $(P \cap Q)^* = P^* \cap Q^*$

Theorem 4.4. Let $P \in U^M$. Then $P \in U(M) \Leftrightarrow P$ hold the following

1. $\hat{N}_{\{0\}} \subseteq P$
2. $rP \subseteq P \forall r \in R$
3. $P + P \subseteq P$

Proof. Consider $P \in U(M)$

1. Consider $\hat{N}_{\{0\}}(x) = \{x, t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), i_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x), f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) : x \in M\}$ where

$$\hat{N}_{\{0\}}(x) = \begin{cases} (1, 1, 0) & x = 0 \\ (0, 0, 1) & x \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

Then obviously, $t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \leq t_P(x)$, $i_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \leq i_P(x)$ and $f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \geq f_P(x) \forall x \in M$

Hence $\hat{N}_{\{0\}} \subseteq P$.

2. Consider $rP = \{x, t_{rP}(x), i_{rP}(x), f_{rP}(x) : x \in M\}$ where

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{rP}(x) &= \begin{cases} \bigvee \{t_P(y)\} & \text{if } y \in M, x = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
 &\leq t_P(x) \forall x \in M [t_P(x) = t_P(ry) \geq t_P(y)]
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly $i_{rP}(x) \leq i_P(x)$, $f_{rP}(x) \geq f_P(x), \forall x \in M$.

Hence $rP \subseteq P$.

3. Consider $x \in M, r \in R$

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{P+P}(x) &= \bigvee \{t_P y \wedge t_P(z) : y, z \in M, x = y + z\} \\
 &\leq t_P(x) \forall x \in M [t_P(x) = t_P(y + z) \geq t_P(y) \wedge t_P(z)]
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $i_{P+P}(x) \leq i_P(x)$ and $f_{P+P}(x) \geq f_P(x)$

Therefore $P + P \subseteq P$.

Conversely, assume $P \in U^M$ satisfies the given three conditions and to show that $P \in U(M)$.

From the condition 1,

$$\hat{N}_{\{0\}} \subseteq P \Rightarrow t_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \leq t_P(x), i_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \leq i_P(x) \text{ and } f_{\hat{N}_{\{0\}}}(x) \geq f_P(x) \forall x \in M \\ \Rightarrow t_P(0) = 1, i_P(0) = 1 \text{ and } f_P(0) = 0.$$

Now for $x, y \in M$,

From condition 3, $P + P \subseteq P$

$$\begin{aligned} t_P(x + y) &\geq t_{P+P}(x + y) \\ &= \vee \{t_P(z_1) \wedge t_P(z_2) : z_1, z_2 \in M, x + y = z_1 + z_2\} \\ &\geq t_P(x) \wedge t_P(y) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $i_P(x + y) \geq i_P(x) \wedge i_P(y)$, $f_P(x + y) \leq f_P(x) \vee f_P(y) \forall x, y \in M$.

Also from condition 2, $\forall r \in R, x \in M$,

$$\begin{aligned} t_P(rx) &\geq t_{rP}(rx) \\ &= \begin{cases} \vee \{t_P(y)\} & \text{if } y = rx, rx = ry \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &\geq t_P(x) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $i_P(rx) \geq i_P(x)$ and $f_P(rx) \leq f_P(x)$.

Therefore it can conclude, $P \in U(M)$. □

Corollary 4.4.1. Let $P \in U^M$, then $P \in U(M) \Leftrightarrow P$ hold the following

1. $\hat{N}_{\{0\}} \subseteq P$
2. $rP + sP \subseteq P, \forall r, s \in R$

5 Conclusion

Neutrosophic submodule is one of the generalizations of the algebraic structure “module” that supplements the classic structure by assigning three diverse level graded features of each module component. This paper presented numerous operations of neutrosophic sets of an R -module M , instigated by the operation addition in M and an action of a ring R on M . The scope and intent of this study are to generalize algebraic structures and to create algebraic neutrosophic structures and find their application. The present study leads to explore the concept of injective and projective neutrosophic submodules of an R -module, semi-simple neutrosophic submodule of an R -module and a quasi neutrosophic submodule of an R -module.

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